

SEE AND BEAM CHARACTERIZATION WITH HIGH ENERGY HEAVY IONS AT HIMAC

Matteo Cecchetto^{1,2} (matteo.cecchetto@cern.ch), K. Bilko¹, N. Emriskova^{1,3}, R. García Alía¹, S. Kodaira⁴, J.-L. Autran⁵

¹CERN (Geneva, CH), ²IM2NP (Aix-Marseille Univ., FR), ³IES (Montpellier Univ., FR), ⁴QST (Chiba, JP), ⁵IPR (Rennes Univ., FR)

1. Abstract

Single event effect cross sections and energy deposition events in a silicon diode were measured with high-energy heavy ions at HIMAC, in Japan, by varying LETs through PMMA degraders. Primary energies of 178 MeV/n ¹³²Xe and 320 MeV/n ⁸⁴Kr were employed. Results were compared to those from other heavy ion facilities, highlighting the importance of facility inter-comparisons. Considerations about single event upset cross sections, measured with and without the package and with fully fragmented beams, are outlined.

2. HIMAC – high-energy heavy ions

- The HIMAC facility, in Ciba (Japan), is primarily dedicated to heavy ion radiotherapy.
- Two test campaigns performed with energies of **178 MeV/n ¹³²Xe** (2024) and **320 MeV/n ⁸⁴Kr** ions (2025), measured at the DUT position.
- Beam structure: pulses every 3.3 s, width of 1 s, size of 6 cm (Xe) and 10 cm (Kr) in diameter with homogeneity of $\pm 5\%$
- Fluence was monitored by means of a **plastic scintillator** next to the DUT.
- **Beam degraded with PMMA slabs** to increase LET.

TABLE I
PMMA THICKNESSES USED DURING THE TESTS WITH THE CORRESPONDING EXIT BEAM ENERGY AND LETS IN Si CALCULATED THROUGH SRIM AND FLUKA. PRIMARY ENERGY OF 178 AND 320 MeV/n FOR ¹³²Xe AND ⁸⁴Kr, RESPECTIVELY. "FRAG" DENOTES FULL BEAM FRAGMENTATION, BASED ON SRIM PREDICTIONS (BLUE, ITALIC) AND ON MEASUREMENTS FROM THIS WORK (BOLD).

Ion	PMMA [mm]	Exit Energy [MeV/n]	LET SRIM [MeVcm ² /mg]	LET FLUKA [MeVcm ² /mg]
¹³² Xe	0	178	11.9	11.2
	3.5	131	14	13.4
	4	122	14.6	14.2
	5	106	16.2	15.3
	5.5	98	17.2	
	6.5	78	20.2	
	7	67	22.7	20.6
	7.5	54	25.4	23.3
	8	39	31.5	28.0
	8.5	19	47.4	
9	-	-	frag ₁	
9.5	-	-	frag ₂	
10.5	-	-	frag ₃	
⁸⁴ Kr	10	320	3.6	3.55
	20	179	5.0	5.25
	25	131	6.1	6.55
	28	95	7.7	8.65
	30	65	9.9	12.95
	30.5	57	11.0	16.15
	31	46	frag ₄ (12.62)	
	31.5	34	frag ₅ (15.44)	
	32	18	frag ₆ (23.17)	

SEU-sensitive SRAMs (DUTs) and diode setup irradiated at HIMAC with Xe and Kr ions.

3. Beam fragmentation assessment

Silicon diode detectors were employed to provide a **fluence measurement** independent of the facility scintillator and to obtain energy deposition spectra for **studying beam fragmentation**.

- Fully fragmented beam with 10.5 mm PMMA.
- Contrary to SRIM simulations (Xe range of 8.78 mm), the beam was **not fully fragmented** with 9 and 9.5 mm PMMAs.

- Contrary to SRIM simulations (Kr range of 32.5 mm), the beam was **already fully fragmented** with 31.5 mm PMMAs.

SEU cross sections obtained with fully fragmented beams are discussed in the paper.

4. DUTs and SEE cross sections

TABLE II
SEE TESTED COTS SRAMs. CYPRESS MEMORY WITH DATE CODES 1713 AND 1919 ARE DELIDDED AND PACKAGED, RESPECTIVELY.

DUT	SEE	Size Mbit	Reference	Date code	Tech. nm
ISSI	SEU	32	IS61WV204816BLL-10TLI	1650	40
Cypress	SEU	16	CY62167GE30-45ZXI	1713-1919	65
Renesas	SEU	8	RMLV0816BGS4-4S2	9062	110
Samsung	SEL	4	K6R4016V1D-TC10	1650	180

- Commercial-off-the-shelf (COTS) SRAMs.
- Powered at 3.3 V.
- Tested in air.
- Room temperature.

- **SEU setup** - memories (with the **package** and without it, i.e. **delidded**). Written with a checkerboard pattern (01) and read/rewritten every 5 s.
- **SEL setup** - memory (with package) in standby mode, current was monitored via software to detect SELs.

HIMAC cross sections compared with those from other heavy ion facilities: RADEF (Jyväskylä, Finland), KVI (Groningen, The Netherlands), GANIL (Caen, France), and HEARTS at CERN (Geneva, Switzerland).

- ISSI (SEU) - Good agreement.
- Cypress (SEU) - Most bit flips at HIMAC due to MBUs rather than SBUs, whereas in other facilities MBUs were negligible.

- Renesas (SEU) - High sensitivity below the expected LET threshold with Kr ions, for LET values calculated with both SRIM and FLUKA.

Impact of the memory package limited in ISSI, and differences up to several factors in Cypress and Renesas memories.

- Samsung (SEL) - high cross sections at lower LET with Kr ions.

5. Conclusions

- SEU and SEL tests on SRAMs performed at HIMAC with **178 MeV/n ¹³²Xe** and **320 MeV/n ⁸⁴Kr** ions.
- Although high-energy heavy ion beams have the advantage of allowing testing in air and without chip decapsulation, **SEU cross section differences** of up to several factors were measured **with the chip package**.
- **Importance of facility inter-comparisons** and potential uncertainties in LET calculations for high-energy beams degraded by significant material thicknesses.
- The results from diode and SRAM measurements indicate that the **SRIM energy and LET values are not accurate near the end of the ion range**.